

Table 2. Evolution of CO₂ in BGA and azolla nurseries at TNRRRI, Aduthurai, India, Jun-Sep 1992.

Source	CO ₂ evolved (mg/m ²)	
	12 h ^a	24 h
Control	120 (10) ^b	240 (10)
BGA nursery	550 (46)	1100 (46)
Azolla nursery	480 (40)	1460 (61)

^a0600-1800. ^bFigures in parentheses denote CO₂ evolved (mg/h per m²).

Biomass and N content of *Sesbania rostrata* mutant with long vegetative phase

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TSR-1 (Trombay *S. rostrata*-1), the late-flowering mutant of *S. rostrata*, remains insensitive to critical inductive photoperiod up to 60 d after planting (DAP). It has the potential to produce sufficient biomass regardless of time of sowing.

We evaluated the performance of TSR-1, the parent cultivar, and local

to atmospheric pollution, increased DOC in water associated with biofertilizers might alleviate problems related to stagnant water. Augmenting DOC in continuously submerged fields where BGA and azolla are grown might also eliminate accumulated reduced iron and sulfides, which are toxic to rice. ■

S. aculeata variety during short-day months of Jan and Feb and long-day months of Jun and Jul. *S. sesban* was included in the Jun-Jul study. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design. Net plot size was 2.3 m². Plant height, fresh weight, percent N, and N/plant were determined at 50 DAP.

TSR-1 was significantly superior to its parent and *S. aculeata* for biomass and N/plant during Jan-Feb (Table 1). During Jun-Jul, TSR-1 performed as well as its parent and the other species for all parameters; it had marginal superiority for N/plant (Table 2). TSR-1 can be grown for biomass production during months of long or short photoperiods. ■

Table 1. Data from yield trial of TSR-1, Jan-Feb, Bombay, India.

Variety/species	Plant height (cm)	Fresh weight (kg/plot)	% N (whole plant)	N/plant (g)
<i>S. rostrata</i>	90.0	2.5	3.7	6.12
TSR-1	126.5	4.1	3.6	9.33
<i>S. aculeata</i>	93.5	1.6	3.6	4.19
LSD (0.05)	18.8	0.5	0.7	2.99

Table 2. Data from yield trial of TSR-1, Jun-Jul, Bombay, India.

Variety/species	Plant height (cm)	Fresh weight (kg/plot)	% N		N/plant (g)
			Leaf	Stem	
<i>S. rostrata</i>	187.5	6.1	5.6	1.7	0.92
TSR-1	186.5	6.0	5.4	1.8	1.22
<i>S. sesban</i>	132.3	6.0	5.4	1.4	0.87
<i>S. aculeata</i>	165.3	5.9	5.2	1.9	1.12
LSD (0.01)	33.8	1.6	0.4	0.6	0.38

Integrated pest management—diseases

Analysis of genetic diversity and population structure of bacterial blight (BB) pathogen in West Java, Indonesia

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BB, caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo), is the most important disease of lowland rice in Indonesia in the wet season. To develop high-yielding varieties with durable resistance to BB, it is necessary to understand the pathogen population structure. We conducted an initial analysis of genetic diversity and population structure of Xoo in West Java using molecular marker techniques.

1. TNX1 haplotypes defined from the Indonesian Xoo isolates (A-D) and the predominant haplotype (III-B) observed for race 3 in Central Luzon, Philippines. M = DNA molecular weight markers.

2. Dendrogram obtained by UPGMA cluster analysis of the six TNX 1 haplotypes defined from the Indonesian Xoo population showing their phylogenetic relationships.

A total of 125 Xoo isolates—51 from the collection maintained in the Plant Pathology Department, Bogor Research Institute for Food Crops, and 74 collected from several fields near Sukamandi and Kuningan in Aug 1992—were subjected to DNA typing by restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) using the DNA probe TNX1 and by digestion with the restriction enzyme *Pst*I.

RFLP analysis using TNX1 revealed six distinct RFLP profiles or haplotypes (Fig. 1). The phylogenetic relationships among these haplotypes were determined by cluster analysis of similarity coefficients by the unweighted pair-group method, arithmetic mean (UPGMA) using the computer program NTSYS. Four distinct lineages were defined at 95% similarity level (Fig. 2). Lineage A, which accounted for 75% of the isolates, had three variants: A, A-1, and A-2. The majority of isolates (68%) were type A. Type A-1, which was observed in 28% of the isolates, was identical to the predominant TNX1 haplotype observed for race 3 in Central Luzon, Philippines. The third variant, A-2, was a rare type and detected in only two isolates (1%) collected from the same field. The three other haplotypes—B, C, and D—were also rare and detected in only one isolate each.

Only 19 of the isolates analyzed (15%) had *Pst*I-digestible DNA. DNA

from the rest of the isolates was uncut by the enzyme. The *Pst*I restriction patterns observed from the Indonesian Xoo isolates were distinct from those seen from the Philippine Xoo isolates.

The total genetic or haplotypic diversity of the Indonesian Xoo population analyzed was estimated using Nei's haplotypic diversity index and found to be low ($H_T=0.47$), based on TNX1-RFLP data. This low level of genetic diversity could be due to rice crop uniformity and stable climatic conditions (no typhoons). The apparent simplicity of Xoo populations in West Java implies that BB in Indonesia might be easy to manage; however, the sample size

analyzed was not large, the collection was not from widely diverse locations, and the phenotypic variation of the population—in terms of virulence on rice hosts carrying different resistance genes—remains to be analyzed.

Further expansion and analysis of the collection, in terms of geographical and host genotype representation, are needed before we can draw firm conclusions. RFLP analysis of a more geographically diverse collection of isolates obtained from different islands of Indonesia is currently underway. Isolates representing each of the RFLP types or groups will be used for evaluating potential sources of resistance to BB in Indonesia. ■

Use of DNA probes to distinguish mycoplasma-like organisms (MLOs) of yellow dwarf (RYD) and orange leaf (ROL) in rice

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The pathogens causing RYD (common in Asia) and ROL (common in Southeast Asia) cannot be distinguished morphologically from each other, although the diseases are different in terms of symptomatology and vector transmissibility. Their taxonomical relationship has not been clarified.

We cloned *Hind*III-cut fragments of chromosomal and extrachromosomal

DNA from the Tochigi line (Japan) of RYD-MLO. The homology of DNA probes with several lines of RYD-MLO and with a Los Baños line of ROL-MLO was examined by dot-blot hybridization. DNA probes were labeled with horseradish peroxidase using the Amersham enhanced chemoluminescence (ECL) system. The DNA-blotted nylon membranes were hybridized with the probes at 42 °C for 16 h in ECL hybridization solutions. The membranes were washed twice at 42 °C for 20 min in 0.5 × SSC (7.5 mM sodium citrate, 75 mM sodium chloride, pH 7.0) containing 6 M urea and 0.4% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), once at 42 °C for 20 min in 0.01 × SSC-0.1% SDS, and once at 42 °C for 20 min in 0.01 × SSC-

Summary of results from dot hybridization of RYD-MLO DNA probes to DNA preparations.^a

Code	Sample	Origin		Chromosomal probes		Extrachromosomal DNA probes		
		Country	Area	R30	R9	R11	R19	R72
H	Healthy rice			-	-	-	-	-
J	RYD-MLO	Japan	Tochigi	+	+	++	++	++
T	RYD-MLO	Thailand	Chachoengsao	+	+	++	++	++
L	RYD-MLO	Philippines	Luzon	+	+	++	++	++
P	RYD-MLO	Philippines	Palawan	+	+	++	++	++
M	RYD-MLO	Philippines	Mindanao	+	+	w	w	w
O	ROL-MLO	Philippines	Los Baños, Laguna	+	-	-	-	-
	Other MLOs ^b			w	-	-	-	-

^a++ = strong hybridization signal, + = moderate hybridization signal, w = weak hybridization signal, - = no hybridization signal. ^bSugarcane white leaf, sesame phyllody (Thailand), onion yellows, cineraria witches' broom, Japanese hornwort witches' broom, water dropwort yellows, gentian witches' broom, udo dwarf, tsuwabuki witches' broom, pelargonium witches' broom (Japan), peach eastern X, and pear decline (USA).